

The Chemistry Scenario in India[†]

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THE main object of the Indian Chemical Society is the cultivation and promotion of chemistry which essentially involves (i) helping to achieve high standard of chemical education in the country, (ii) fostering the growth of chemical industry for national needs in general and appropriate technology for rural development in particular, (iii) accelerating the pace of genuine and internationally recognised chemical research and (iv) arranging publication of research results, ensuring their quality and credibility.

In fulfilling its social and political obligations, the Society must acquire the capacity and competence to win recognition from the Government to be able to advise them in research funding policies and programmes. Also it has to win the confidence of big business-houses to be able to help its fellow-members in job-seeking and proper placement according to expertise of the member concerned.

The Annual Convention is an appropriate time to consider whether the Indian Chemical Society is proceeding in the right direction and whether its activity-chart would enable it to play its role in serving the cause of the nation, nay the community at-large through the application of chemistry to sustain growth and development. However there are other fora and societies which share the responsibility regarding industrial applications of chemistry. Government recognition has not yet come partly due to nepotism practised by certain group of scientists occupying the corridors of power in governmental/scientific agencies and partly due to erosion of credibility caused by internecine troubles in the ranks of the Chemical Society.

Notwithstanding these, the Society should have launched programmes for standardisation of chemical education which it sadly neglected. The poor standards of chemical education obtaining in the country are primarily due to ill-equipped laboratories and poor curricula. Vested interests bar recruitment of really brilliant and highly motivated teachers in the university departments. Such teachers can hardly inspire the students. To attract better teachers to the profession, the Government must consider granting the teaching/research community, if no perks, if on privileges, at least special consumer rights and special passenger rights to make their living smooth. That would save them waiting in long queue at the fair-price shops and bus/railway stations and hence enable them to concentrate on the professional readiness.

In the context of fostering quality research, the Society can hardly play any physical role as it has neither any laboratory of its own nor do its finances permit giving grant for any individual/group research project. The little that is possible within its limited funds, it does provide fora for exchange of research information as also in depth discussion by organising/co-sponsoring at frequent intervals at national and sometimes at international levels symposia, workshops, seminars and conferences. The Society does publish the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society. There is imperative need to improve this Journal. That would improve the image of the Society.

The present state of chemical research in India presents a very dismal picture. To elaborate one may talk in terms of work in conventional branches of chemistry, namely physical, organic and inorganic. Physical chemistry laboratories in most of the Indian Universities are ill-equipped. While workers abroad have easy access to the use of lasers, synchrotron radiation source of energy and super computers for studying structure and dynamics of chemical systems, the Indian physical chemists have to rest content with only traditional gadgets. Consequently very scarce mention of their work is found in the literature on outstanding contributions in the study of new material exhibiting super conducting properties, catalytic surfaces and solids, the nature of liquid state and dynamics in the pico seconds range. In the field of organic chemistry, a large amount of good quality work has been reported from Indian laboratories but hardly any major synthesis or reaction have emanated whereas the work abroad abounds in triumphs of structural investigation and syntheses of a host of complex organic molecules including bio-molecules. The inorganic chemistry experienced a renaissance a few decades ago and its frontiers now overlap with metalloprotein chemistry, biomimetic chemistry, ion transport through membrane and photoproduction of energy. The inorganic chemists in India have hardly any facility to work in these frontier areas of chemistry.

In fact, lack of facility for instrumentation has been the biggest obstacle for high quality research work in this country. For example, high resolution and sophisticated instruments for nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, Mössbauer spectroscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy became available in our country much later than the workers abroad had substantially exploited these. The facilities

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were made available around sixties in some national laboratories, research institutes and I.I.T.s which were created to be the prize institutions but most of these institutions were created outside the university system leading to impoverishment of these natural repositories of intellect where young scientists can be trained in sufficiently large numbers to man and manage such specialised establishments. The university system has therefore to be given proper attention and also it should be revamped in the context of the "New Education Policy". "There is imperative need for emphasis on training our young scientists in instrumentation on the one hand, and a deep awareness of learning theoretical treatment of research problems on the other for improving the quality of research. Only then we can expect any major breakthrough in future which has been sadly very rare in the past half-a-century of work. Something has to be done to minimise emphasis on proliferation of mundane research papers and unhealthy race for producing Ph.D.s. The entire process of investigation including "everything from identification of the problem to assessment of validity of results, through a whole gamut of selection of methodology, selection of instrumentation, delineation of protocol, execution of protocol, the reduction of data and development of constructs leading to results" must be very deftly handled. A concerted effort has to be made to identify thrust areas with special reference to national relevance and convert the scientific talent available in the country into a task force dedicated to investigate those areas of scientific research. Adequate funding must be made available by the Government. Some work has been done in this direction by the SERC. The work must be entrusted to really talented individuals.

It is an established fact that basic research is carried out by and around gifted individuals. Educationally, this has a bearing on teacher-pupil relationship. The adventures in science are replete with examples where based on "Guru-Shishya" relationship, geneologies can be traced. Taking examples from chemistry, Leibig was a pupil of the great French chemist Gay-Lussac who in turn was a pupil of Berthollet. From Leibig can be traced successive generations of scores of Nobel Prize winners in chemistry including Kekule. A similar geneology of teacher-pupil family can be traced from Von Bayer to Otto Warburg to Emil Fisher to Hans Gebs and several other distinguished chemists. These are the names in chemistry without whose pioneering work, the science of chemistry would have remained in the Alchemy stage. Hardwork, incessant toil, perseverance, self-critical mind and above all an attitude of humility have been the corner-stone for brilliant achievements of these highly talented teachers and their pupils. The great educationist, J. B. Conant has said that there is only one proved method of assisting advancement of pure science and that is picking men of geneous, backing them heavily and leaving them to direct themselves. Even small groups around gifted men would be able to deliver the goods better than high investment-intensive

large institutions. The policy makers and administrators would do well to have these considerations in mind while planning for future. Identification of sincere workers in our country needs a lot of attention as the present sorry state of affairs in chemical research is a direct consequence of favouritism and nepotism in allocation of grants in many cases to individuals who are not really deserving. Many deserving ones have been denied their dues.

The boost that science and technology received consequent to declaration of science policy, technology policy, ocean policy, energy policy by the Government of India has certainly helped in ushering an era of industrial and technological development in the country. Achievements in some fields like atomic energy research, defence research and space research have been highly impressive. But in spite of rapid quantitative increase in science and scientific man-power and enormous investment in science and technology, the peaks of excellence have been rare. The points of flow of excellence unfortunately appear to have dried up. It seems that too much emphasis on equality and democracy have helped the circumstances to operate against the development of excellence in science. Quality has been the worst victim. It is imperative therefore that steps be taken to strengthen quality at every level of scientific research to prepare the generation to meet the challenges of the twenty-first century.

The edifice of scientific knowledge consists of "a data base, an array of methodologies and an array of concepts". In the same logic, technology can be looked upon as "the process of production and delivery of goods and services encompassing everything from concept to successful delivery". The body of knowledge thus amounts to "a data base, an array of methodologies and an array of concepts". The two processes of science and technology therefore would be synergistic in acquisition of knowledge. The debate regarding basic versus applied research should be stopped. In fact, "basic research is an integral component of a self-reliant base of science and technology" and first rate minds are needed both for basic and applied research.

The science of chemistry has largely aided the progress and development in most spheres. Advances in medical science with powerful antibiotics and miracle drugs have increased life expectancy. The green revolution in agriculture has enabled food production to keep pace with population explosion. Developments in biotechnology hold out an unending chain of new possibilities. It is no more necessary to extract insulin and pituitary growth hormone from animal pancreas and human pituitaries. The gene-cloning may be used for making antiviral drugs, interferon and purified immunising vaccines against harmful agents. Attempts are being made to introduce known genes which specify nitrogen-fixing mechanisms from bacteria directly and permanently into the genetic apparatus of the cereal plants. The possible development of a superconducting material may transform the entire energy

scenario. Hot out of the test tube reports about cold fusion in chemical laboratories, when fully substantiated would usher changes in physical and chemical concepts beyond comprehension at present. It seems man has reached a stage in evolution when his very survival and future evolution is possible only on the basis of science.

It must be remembered that these advances in physical sciences and material benefits thereof have led to social expectations on the one hand, and induced life-style changes, creating diverse cultural ethos in society on the other hand. "There is more and more emphasis on devoting to the technologies of production, technique of coordinating man, machine and material, logic of national tasks and economic planning". This is calculated to achieve the twin goals of rising standards of living and establishing socio-economic justice. While it is desirable that the intellectual, economic and administrative orientation of our society lean on the cognitive maps of this science and technology born developmental

ethos, it is equally important that "the emotive maps of our culture should continue to define not only the system of sentience and being but also the structure of becoming and other attendant task of national goal". We have to save our Society from fragmentation which is threatening our very social fabric. We have to see that the current transience generated by proneness of our society to keep borrowing newer developments in technologies and socio-political ideologies is not permitted to widen the gap between the emotive and cognitive maps. Integration and proper consolidation must be allowed for simulation of new technologies. "Social phenomenology, dys-functionalities and deviances should be recalibrated" and "resilience of the social design should be kept alive to sustain a diversity of forms and behaviour and yet create a psychocultural identity with diverse ethos". The emerging culture of "transition and transience should give way to a new process which can establish convergence and congruence and provide us with a sense of well-being while moving towards newer frontiers of science and technology".